

Significance, risk and the maintenance of Engineering and Industrial Objects

– a continuing discussion.

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National Museum of
Australia

Objector Artifact

ANDRA
PRO SERIES
DRAG RACING
Willowbank Raceway

one HD one HD

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NMA consequences assessment

NMA Functional objects Planning Tool

Running a Museum: A Practical Handbook
Care and Preservation of Collections

Figure 1. The collection preservation cycle, that must be coordinated within other museum planning cycles.

Risk?
Per second
or
per 100 years

Approach

The background of the slide is a photograph of a boat's engine compartment. The engine is a dark-colored, four-cylinder unit. To the left, there is a black battery with yellow and red terminals. Various hoses, including red and black ones, are connected to the engine. The surrounding structure is painted a vibrant blue. The lighting is somewhat dim, highlighting the metallic and plastic components.

Our aim should be to find the rate limiting steps for minimising deterioration while maximising use and preservation.

As with other cultural items the conservation and maintenance of functional objects should acknowledge engineering culture, it's values and aspirations.

What's "best" for the object?

- Non Functional
- Maintained
- Static
- Functional?—
- Storage/exhibition and limited use?

Operation Without planning
or non use without thought
are both
maximising the risk of loss

What happens in original oil and hydraulic systems over 100 years?
We remove chlorides from maritime objects why not replace fluids with inhibitors?

A Study of Functional Fluids in Static vehicles at Coventry Transport Museum

In total we sampled

- 30 Brake and Clutch fluids samples
- 31 Coolant samples
- 11 Engine oil samples
- 4 Power-steering oil samples
- 3 Automatic Transmission oil samples
- 6 Gearbox oil samples
- 2 Differential oil samples
- 2 Stale fuel samples

Total of 89 samples

Cooling System Corrosion

Bentley

Fig 11 -exhaust valve open

Fig 12 corrosion around closed valve

Fig 13 Corrosion on bore liner closed valves

Fig 14 oxidation lines on bore wall open valves

Bentley 1924

Cylinder N°1 T.B.C
opposite plug Valves
closed

Cylinder N°2 B.D.C piston
crown

Cylinder N°2 scoring on
thrust side

Cylinder No 2 Bore &
scoring and corrosion

Corrosion valve N°2
Cylinder

Exhaust valve open

Exhaust ports

Bentley 1924

Fluid: Engine oil (probably st/30)

Last driven: June 1980

Photographs: Michiel Brunott

Photographs: copyright Coventry Transport Museum

- **Significance** is a difficult term to define in a museum context. What makes something worthy of preservation for the greater good of humanity?

See

<http://significance.collectionscouncil.com.au>

- Significance and Value are interchangeable words
- In Australia we use Significance particularly “significance 2”

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Figure 1. The collection preservation cycle, that must be coordinated within other museum planning cycles.

NMA consequences assessment

- Excel spread sheet that allows you to look at risk significance and the consequences in a numeric manner.

How soon? (rate, or probability, of damage)

Risks that occur as distinct events

Risks that accumulate gradually

3

Occurs about once every year

Damage occurs in about 1 year

2

Occurs about once in 10 years

Damage occurs in about 10 years

1

Occurs about once in 100 years

Damage occurs in about 100 years

0

Occurs about once in 1000 years

Damage occurs in about 1000 years

How much damage to each affected system? (proportional loss of value)

3

Total or almost total loss of system (100%)

2

Significant but limited damage to each system (10%)

1

Moderate or reversible damage to each system (1%)

0

Just observable damage to the system (0.1%)

How much of the system is affected? (fraction of collection at risk)

3

All or most of the system (100%)

2

A large fraction of the system (10%)

1

A small fraction of the system (1%)

0

One component of a system (0.1% or less)

How important are the affected systems? (value of artefacts at risk)

3

Much higher than average significance (100 times the average value)

2

Higher than average significance (10 times the average value)

1

Average significance for this collection

0

Lower than average value for this collection (1/10 the average value)

What aspects are important Artefact or Object?

Top Fuel Drag
racer
basic template

unmaintained storage

risk of damage or failure

Total
risk

Primary criteria (significance 2)

- Historic significance 2
- Artistic or aesthetic significance 2
- Scientific or research significance 1
- Social or spiritual significance 2

Plus

- Functional Significance 3

How soon?
How much damage to each affected system?
How much of the system is affected?
How important are the affected systems?

	How soon?	How much damage to each affected system?	How much of the system is affected?	How important are the affected systems?	Total risk
Bodywork and interior	3	1	2	2	8
Engine and Transmission	3	3	3	3	12
Brake and hydrologic System	3	3	3	3	12
Electrical System	2	2	2	2	8
Cooling System	3	3	3	2	11
Chassis, suspension and Wheels	3	2	3	3	11

consequences possible

62
72

consequences

Storage and limited use

A man in a white long-sleeved shirt and dark pants stands in a studio, holding a camera on a tripod. He is positioned next to a blue bus that has been transformed into a large-scale mural. The bus is covered in colorful, abstract artwork. The studio has a green screen on the left and a dark background with some lighting equipment visible on the right. The bus has a sign that reads "THE PEACE BUS P.N.D." on its side.

The basic approach is that objects spend most time in storage/display.

They have limited but periodic use and maintenance.

Frequency depends on -materials based- conservation requirements and public programs demand.

Maintenance

- Typical maintenance will entail.
- Running the object to operating temperature for 30 minutes
- Changing fluids –filling tires with nitrogen
- Adjusting and tuning
- Monitoring
- Cycling all systems.

NMA Functional objects Planning Tool

- We are trying to improve the development of the planning tool used by the NMA
- Our current model is based on Johanna Barr's work mixed with our risk and significance based approach
- This is a project in development!

The Tool

- Planning
- Implementation
- Feedback

Monitoring and feedback

- Monitoring
- Reporting
- Feedback – to implementation
- Publication - feedback to community

Monitoring

- XRF
- pH
- Conductivity
- Smell
- Taste

PeakID
Clear All Elem MoKa1 Elem List: MoKa1
Add Del Z- Z+

PDZ Preview

Path	OK
10-6-09-pt-3.pdz	
10-6-09-pt-4.pdz	
10-6-09-pt-5.pdz	
10-6-09-pt-6.pdz	
10-6-09-pt-9.pdz	
15-0609-bf.pdz	
15-06-09-bk.pdz	
15-06-09-co.pdz	
15-0609-csly-2.pdz	
15-0609-csly-3.pdz	
15-0609-csly-4.pdz	
15-0609-csly-5.pdz	
15-0609-csly-6.pdz	
15-0609-csly-7.pdz	
15-06-09-dl-s.pdz	
15-06-09-ee.pdz	
15-06-09-go-ep.pdz	
15-06-09-sm.pdz	

Prototype Holden

Methods and Materials Choice

Fig 19 seized slave cylinder

Fig 20 half removed piston

Fig 21 slave cylinder bore

Fig 22 oxidized wheel piston

Fig 23 pitting on master cylinder piston

Fig 29, Green solid on edge of aluminium strip and screw

Figure 1: An Assortment of brake fluids to be tested for suitability in a museum environment.

PROPERTY	DOT 3	DOT 4	DOT 5	DOT 5.1
Dry Boil Point (ERBP)	205°C	230°C	260°C	260°C
Wet Boil Point (Wet ERBP)	140°C	155°C	180°C	180°C
Chemical Composition	Glycol	Glycol	Silicone	Glycol
Viscosity (-40°C) mm ² /s max	1500	1800	900	900

Table 1: Requirements for brake fluid classification according to DOT standards. NOTE ERBP= Equilibrium Reflux Boiling Point.

Figure 6: Elevated temperature experimental setup

Figure 10: Graph showing relationship between corrosion rate and brake fluid concentration covering the entire range from pure water to pure brake fluid. Results obtained via the tafel approach with mild steel electrode.

Figure 7: Experimental setup for Tafel approach.

Figure 12: Comparison of corrosion protection offered by various fluids used with steel electrode

XRF Comparison of Holden Prototype oil vs Standard base oil after

Figure 2. Comparison of Holden Prototype No.1 engine oil vs standard after controlled maintenance run for 100km at Oran Park race track Sydney NSW. Note the Fe and Mo residues from a previous engine rebuild using MoS2 grease in the rebuild process.

1926 Bean car after 10 years display

Oil pump pre Screen
Note lack of carbon and corrosion.

Conrod locknut.
Note lack of sludge or carbon build-up

Web of crankshaft
Note oil film and cleanness of oil

Cylinder wall through spark plug hole

Oil dripping off bottom end
Note how clean oil is

Crankshaft and crank web
Note old stain but no red rust

Crown wheel in differential

Crankcase Water Jacket
Note deposits but no red rust

Cylinder head Water Jacket
Note start of failure brown globules are present in small numbers

Bean 1926

Fluid: Penrite Shelsley Medium

XRF Comparison of oil after 10 years maintained display

Figure 5. Comparison of Bean car engine oil after 10 years' display and basic periodic maintenance against a current new standard. The "slight variation" is due to bromine that was used as a lead scavenger in the leaded petrol this car ran on in the 1950's.

Foundation HAM (Historical Army Material) contracted by the Swiss Federal Department of Defence, Civil Protection and Sport, is responsible for the conservation, restoration and maintenance of the historical wheeled and tracked vehicle collection of the Swiss military.

The collection contains over 700 vehicles (of which about 600 have an engine) and is composed of:

- Horse carriages
- Cycles
- Motorcycles
- Jeeps
- Trucks
- Tanks
- Trailers
- Aggregates

The foundation is currently carrying out a feasibility study to determine whether it is possible to carry out a maintenance scheme on such a big number of vehicles.

This is the protocol as it is being carried out:

- Two vehicles are chosen
- Fluid levels and brakes are checked and vehicles inspected for any obvious problems
- Vehicles are taken to the workshop for another more detailed inspection
- The vehicles are driven for exactly 35km over a set out route with two stops for intermediary checks

Back at the workshop

- The ridden mileage is entered in the logbook of the vehicle
- A condition report is established
- Afterwards vehicles are put back on their initial place

Conclusions

.We have outlined a developing approach to the conservation, maintenance and use of our working collection that incorporates assessment of significance and risk.

We have developed a consequence assessment which we believe will be useful in assessing storage, exhibition and use of functional objects.

Conclusions

- We have highlighted the importance of analytical research and the gathering of statistical data in developing a flexible maintenance program for each functional object.
- We will continue to develop and consolidate these approaches in collaboration with others Nationally and Internationally

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Questions

1995 - How have we progressed?

